

PREDICT-6G

[D2.4]

Implementation of selected release 2 PREDICT-6G
MDP innovations

PREDICT-6G

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Abstract

This document includes the final implementations of the MDP innovations selected from D2.3. As part of this document, the code to provide determinism in the data plane for different domains is also delivered.

Keywords

Multi-domain, TSN, MDP, Data-plane, DetNet, 802.1Qbv, 3GPP

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R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	3GPP 3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GS	5G System
ACK	Acknowledgment
ADU	Application Data Unit
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AICP	AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ARP	Address Resolution Protocol
BS	Base Station
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CHO	Conditional Handover
CU	Central Unit
CUC	Centralized User Configuration
DAPS	Dual Active Protocol Stack
DCF	Distributed Coordination Function
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DL	Downlink
DNC	DetNet Controller
DNR	DetNet Router
DoA	Description of Action
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DSCP	Differentiated Services Code Point
DS-TT	Device Side Time-Sensitive Networking Translator

DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
DUG	Data Unit Group
E2E	End-to-End
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ESP-IDF	Espressif IoT Development Framework
FRER	Frame replication and elimination for reliability
gNB	gNodeB
HO	Handover
HOF	Handover Failures
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IIR	Infinite Impulse Response
InF	Indoor Factory
IP	Internet Protocol
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
L1	Layer 1
L2	Layer 2
L3	Layer 3
LTM	Lower Layer Triggered Mobility
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LoS	Line of Sight
LMMSE	Linear Minimum Mean Square Error
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MA	Measurement Agents
MAC	Media Access Control layer
MAC-CE	MAC Control Element

MDP	Multi-domain Data-Plane
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLO	Multi-Link Operation
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit
MS	Managed Service
NDT	Network Digital Twin
NN	Neural Network
NR	New Radio
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
NW-TT	Network Side Time-Sensitive Networking Translator
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access
PCell	Primary Cell
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDU	Packet Data Unit
PHY	Physical layer
PP	Ping-pong events
PREOF	Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functionality
PSCell	Primary Secondary cell
QoE	Quality of Experience
RLC	Radio Link Control layer
RLP	Radio Link Problems
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
R-TAG	Redundancy Tag
RTT	Round Trip Time

SBI	Service-Based Interface
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
S-label	Service Label
SP	Service Period
SSB	Synchronization Signal Block
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
STA	Station
TA	Timing Advance
TBTT	Target Beacon Transmission Time
TDD	Time Division Duplexing
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access
TSCTSF	Time Sensitive Communication and Time Synchronization Function
TSF	Timing Synchronization Function
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TWT	Target Wake Time
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
VLAN	Virtual Local-Area Network
VR	Virtual Reality
VxLAN	Virtual eXtensible Local-Area Network
WP	Work Package
XDP	eXpress Data Path
XR	eXtended Reality
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
NOK	Nokia Solutions and Networks KFT
ERC	Ericsson Espana SA
INT	Intel Deutschland GMBH
TID	Telefonica Investigacion Digital SL
ATOS	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
GES	Gestamp Servicios SA
NXW	Nextworks
COG	Cognitive Innovations Private Company
SIM	Software Imagination & Vision SRL
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Alpha Lab MTU
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
UPC	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
UNIPD	Universita degli Studi di Padova
IDE	InterDigital Europe LTD

1 Executive summary

This document presents the final implementations of the Multi-domain Data-Plane (MDP) innovations described in Deliverable D2.3 [1] reflecting the advancements from the initial implementations reported in Deliverable D2.2 [2]. The focus of these implementations is to introduce determinism in the data plane across different wired and wireless technology domains, within the scope of PREDICT-6G project, where determinism is defined as the union of reliability, time sensitiveness and predictability.

This deliverable includes fundamental research to achieve this type of determinism, through developments in dynamic scheduling algorithms, predictive models for handover (HO) decisions in 3GPP, Data Unit Groups (DUG) for packet processing on Deterministic Networking (DetNet) routers, AI models for seamless roaming through Wi-Fi 7's Multi-Link Operation (MLO), extensions for the operation of 5G systems as Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) bridges, and the implementation of IEEE 802.1Qbv for enhanced traffic management. It also addresses the challenges of flow monitoring in non-deterministic domains and the integration of DetNet with end-to-end data plane services.

This deliverable is complemented with multiple implementations of the different innovations described herein, which are available (subject to constraints from the different partners) in different code repositories indicated in the respective section.

The following key innovations are approached and included in the current report:

- **Dynamic Schedulers for Mixed Traffic:** Addressing the allocation of uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) resources in 5G networks, with a focus on optimizing the scheduling of time-sensitive and best-effort traffic flows.
- **Time-Based Schedulers on 3GPP:** Extending the capabilities of 5G systems to support TSN operations, ensuring time synchronization and reduced latency for critical applications.
- **TSN Redundancy:** Enhancing the resilience of networks to interference and attacks, ensuring reliable communication for time-sensitive applications.
- **IEEE 802.1Qbv Implementations:** Implementing traffic management mechanisms to support real-time and best-effort traffic, with a focus on offset synchronization and latency evaluation.
- **Flow Monitoring:** Developing methods for monitoring traffic flows in domains where determinism cannot be guaranteed, ensuring quality of service for diverse applications.

- **DetNet Implementation:** Integrating DetNet capabilities to provide deterministic services across the data plane, from Layer 2 to Layer 3, and ensuring end-to-end performance.
- **Data Unit Groups (DUGs):** Increasing reliability, making possible that a DetNet router can use DUG metadata to process packets belonging to the same traffic flow.
- **5G systems as TSN bridges:** Developing of a software TSN switch that is key for testing TSN capabilities on top of non-TSN networks (e.g., 3GPP networks Release 15).

Finally, this deliverable lists the Open APIs used to integrate the MDP with the PREDICT-6G Control Plane, including the corresponding code repository.

2 Introduction

The current document provides details about the second release of the implementation phase of the multi-domain data plane (MDP) innovations approached by PREDICT-6G, including the advancements and results achieved since the first release of MDP in D2.2 in November 2023 ([2]).

The structure of this deliverable maintains continuity with D2.2 in sections 3, 4 and 5. Section 3 is dedicated to fundamental research innovations and their implementations, Section 4 presents standalone demonstrations, while Section 5 presents integrated demonstrations.

Section 6 provides details about the implementation of OpenAPIs provided by the MDP towards the AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP). The section refers to the further description of the time synchronization, deterministic service provisioning, exposure and measurement APIs included in D2.3 in December 2024 ([1]) and points to the formal specification accessible in PREDICT-6G's GitLab [3].

Appendix A at the end of the document contains a list with the implementation code for each MDP innovation.

3 Fundamental Research

3.1 Dynamic Scheduling

In section 3.2 of document D2.3 [1], the slice-aware Time Division Duplexing-Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (TDD-OFDMA) radio resource allocation procedures based on 3GPP, that included multiuser distribution of UL and DL subchannels as well as the admission control and rate adjustment of best-effort services were described. The evaluation is implemented in the UPC Matlab-based system simulator uploaded in gitlab (please check 9.1), whose structure is displayed in Figure 3-1. Both the integration of traffic types into the Radio Resource Management (RRM) procedures, and the simulated industrial scenario are described below.

Figure 3-1: UPC-DS1. Structure of the Matlab L1-L2 simulator for the evaluation of slice-aware TDD-OFDMA radio resource management procedures.

Traffic modelling and transmission rate constraints

In the resource allocation techniques described in D2.3 [1], the latency, rate and jitter allocated to flows are translated into transmission rate constraints for the optimization problem assuming M/M/1 queuing models, which may not necessarily match the actual traffic patterns. More generally, the adoption of a general model-free queuing dynamics that captures the link between latency constraint and transmission rate at the L1 is proposed here.

For general non-exponential distributions of the waiting time D of packets in a queue both Markov's inequality and Little's theorem could be adopted to write:

$$\Pr\{D > D_i^{max}\} \leq \frac{E\{D\}}{D_i^{max}} = \frac{L}{a_i D_i^{max}}$$

where D_i^{max} is the maximum allowed delay for the i -th flow, a_i is its packet arrival rate and L is the average queue length. What is interesting is to bound the probability of delay exceeding the maximum with a low probability $(1 - \gamma)$, in this way the average queue length as $L \leq (1 - \gamma)D_i^{max}a_i$ should be enforced. The proposal, since the M/M/1 assumption is being dropped, is to link a_i and the minimum transmission rate $r_{o,i}$ through a time recursive estimate of the average queue length:

$$\hat{L}(t + 1) = \hat{L}(t) + \kappa (q(t) - \hat{L}(t))$$

where $\kappa \hat{I}(0,1)$ is a learning rate and $q(t)$ is the instantaneous queue length that contains the transmission and arrival rates as:

$$q(t) = q(t - 1) - \min(r_{o,i}(t)\Delta t, q(t - 1)) + a_i\Delta t$$

In this equation Δt is the time interval granted to serve the queue of the i -flow at rate $r_{o,i}(t)$, which is in practice the scheduling period. This way a non-biased estimate of the average queue length whose variance grows with the value of κ is obtained. With the goal of adjusting the transmission rate, the condition $\hat{L}(t + 1) = (1 - \gamma)D_i^{max}a_i$ combined with the previous equations provides a closed form expression for the target rate:

$$r_{o,i}(t) = \frac{q(t - 1)}{\Delta t} + \min\left(a_i - \frac{(1 - \gamma)D_i^{max}a_i - (1 - \kappa)\hat{L}(t)}{\kappa\Delta t}, 0\right)$$

That is, the rate $r_{o,i}(t)$ can be smaller than the value required to empty the queue if the product $(1 - \gamma)D_i^{max}$ is large enough. Otherwise, the queue is emptied in each scheduling period. On the other hand, Chebyshev's inequality provides a bound for the instantaneous jitter J_i suffered by a packet:

$$\Pr\{|D - E\{D\}| \geq J_i\} \leq \frac{varD}{J_i^2}$$

Unfortunately, there is no parallel Little's theorem that link the variance of the delay and the queue length. Expressions for the jitter only exist for M/M/c, M/G/1 or M/D/1 models, not for the general arrival and departure packet models. Therefore, simple expressions for online estimation of $var\{D\}$ cannot be used, and we must resort to the expression of M/M/1 case (which unfortunately it is not a universal bound for the variance of other cases):

$$\text{var}\{D\} = \frac{1}{(r_{o,i}(t) - a_i)^2} \leq J_i^2$$

From here we can obtain the value $r_{o,i}(t)$ required for the allocation of OFDMA resources. For services demanding latency and jitter constraints, the required transmission rate $r_{o,i}(t)$ is obviously the most restrictive one.

Robust scheduling

The power allocation strategy for DL and UL detailed in D2.3 [1] is effective for maximizing system throughput, but such approach inherently assigns less transmit power per subcarrier to terminals near the gNB and more power to those at the cell edge. This can result in strong signals intended for distant terminals causing receiver saturation at nearby receivers, which are not the intended recipients. The resulting power disparity can degrade performance for receivers in proximity, increase inter-user interference, and lead to inefficient utilization of the available transmit power. To address these challenges, we propose an alternative approach that allocates equal power to all subcarriers, irrespective of the distance of the user from the gNB. This strategy not only streamlines real-time power control and resource scheduling but also enhances user fairness by ensuring uniform energy distribution across subcarriers. Additionally, it alleviates front-end receiver impairments such as overload and non-linear distortion, thereby reducing the risk of saturation in terminals located near the base station.

The optimization problem is reformulated to minimize the maximum power allocated per subchannel while ensuring fairness and maintaining the required data rates for all users.

To uncouple the optimum subcarrier allocation and the equal power allocation, we adopt three different strategies to allocate subcarriers that ensures convergence to the required rate constraints: 1) use the optimum subcarrier allocation (EPA- X_{DL}), 2) use an adhoc reallocation of subcarriers from users with surplus rates to those struggling to meet their rate requirements (EPA- $X_{DL+Realloc}$), or 3) use the Hungarian algorithm to allocate subcarriers (EPA- X_{HA}). This dynamic reallocation process is designed to improve power efficiency and optimize overall resource utilization. A comparison of the different approaches is shown for the downlink in the following subsection.

Simulated scenario

The OFDMA UL/DL dynamic scheduling described in document D2.3 [1] is tested in a smart factory environment. The propagation scenario chosen for this work is a washing industry used to wash, dry clean, and store large batches of textile products. Figure 3-2 shows the 3D digital model of the propagation scenario in the channel emulator. The factory floor is 210 m long, 97 m wide, and 5 m high and is divided into three zones differing in terms of shape, size, object

material, and clutter density. This scenario corresponds to a typical 3GPP Indoor Factory (InF) scenario.

Figure 3-2: 3D digital model of the propagation scenario.

The area of focus is Zone B: it is 78.6 m long, filled with 4.4 height metallic storage racks stacked with wooden boxes. Metallic storage racks are one of the most common industrial objects, thus making them a suitable choice for the analysis. This design does not correspond to an actual factory but represents a virtual test scenario in which realistic positions, heights, and deployments were selected.

For our evaluation, a factory area of size 97×36 m² in Zone B with an increased number of storage racks to depict a densely cluttered warehouse of a factory was selected as depicted in Figure 3-3. Single-input single-output (SISO) channel samples from an omni-directional gNB and 850 user equipment (UE) positions are generated. The base station (BS) is placed 5 meters above the ground (just under the ceiling) and 1 meter away from the walls while the UEs' positions are uniformly distributed in a grid with a resolution of 2 meters resulting in a density of 0.25 UE/m². All users are positioned at a height of 1.5 meters above the ground. The channel samples used in this study are part of a massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) channel samples database generated from 15 omni-directional BSs. The in-factory ray-tracing channel dataset was produced by Siradel using the Volcano software channel generator ([4], [5]). Channel predictions are made for BS and UEs equipped with dual-polar (V/H) antenna arrays operating at 3.7 GHz. The MIMO channel matrix is computed for each resource block as it is verified using simulations that, for this scenario, the coherence bandwidth is less than the bandwidth of a subchannel (considering 5G NR numerology 1). The focus was on SISO channel samples.

Figure 3-3:UPC-DS3. Study area with the BS (in yellow) and 850 possible UE positions (in red).

The figure below displays the performance in terms of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for four strategies for OFDMA radio resource management in the DL under the traffic configuration proposed in document D2.3, over 10000 MonteCarlo realizations of UE positions in the coverage area. Results in the left plot show near optimum performance of the equal power allocation with suboptimal allocation of subcarriers with later reallocation ($X_{DL+Realloc}$), in terms of transmitted power. As compared to other suboptimal approaches with no reallocation (X_{DL}) or Hungarian algorithm allocation (X_{HA}), we some 15 dB power savings. The right plot shows the CDF of the energy efficiency in joules per transmitted bit.

Figure 3-4: Cumulative functions of the transmitted power (left) and the energy efficiency (right) in the downlink for the optimal power and resource allocation as compared to robust strategies avoiding near-far effects at the UE receivers.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/dynamic-scheduling-upc>

3.2 Predictive handover decisions for 3GPP

The research on mobility focuses on optimizing seamless connectivity, mobility and ensuring deterministic communication by leveraging predictive models for handover decisions. As in deterministic communication networks maintaining strict latency and reliability requirements is crucial, making efficient handover management a key challenge. Unplanned or suboptimal handovers can lead to disruptions, increased latency, and degraded quality of service. To address these issues, the proposed models are specifically trained to enhance key performance indicators (KPIs) related to the connection quality between user equipment (UE) and 3GPP base stations (gNB), ensuring uninterrupted and time-sensitive data transmission. The focus is specifically on inter-frequency handover triggered by low-quality received signals.

3.2.1 Mobility and handover in 3GPP

New Radio (NR) supports different types of handovers. The basic handover in NR is based on the Long-Term Evolution (LTE) handover mechanism in which the network controls UE mobility based on UE measurement reporting. In the basic handover, a source gNB triggers handover by sending a handover request to a target gNB, and after receiving an acknowledgment (ACK) from the target gNB, the source gNB initiates handover by sending a handover command with target cell configuration. Once the handover command is received, the UE detaches from the

serving cell and initiates random access to the target cell indicated by the network. The UE accesses the target cell after the target cell configuration is applied.

In the NR high-frequency range with beamforming, when the UE moves or rotates, the UE can experience signal degradation. The channel condition between line of sight (LoS) and non-LoS in NR may be very different as well. It may result in higher handover failure, (e.g., as UE may not receive the expected radio resource control (RRC) message to trigger handover due to poor signal conditions). Conditional Handover (CHO) has been introduced to improve the reliability of handover. The CHO is a handover procedure that is executed only when the configured CHO execution condition(s) are met. The UE maintains the connection with source gNB after receiving the CHO configuration and starts evaluating the CHO execution conditions for the candidate cells. In CHO the UE does not send a report nor waits for the network handover decision. Instead, the UE takes the handover decision autonomously based on L3-filtered cell quality measurements (PL3) or L1-filtered reference signal received power (RSRP) measurements (PL1). If at least one CHO candidate cell satisfies the corresponding CHO execution condition, the CHO is executed by detaching from the source gNB, applying the corresponding configuration for the selected candidate cell, and accessing the target cell.

Dual Active Protocol Stack (DAPS) handover has been introduced to achieve zero-ms interruption time during handover to support ultra-reliable low latency communication (URLLC) type of service, which requires very low end-to-end delay. The DAPS handover allows a user to initiate a handover to a target cell while maintaining the connection with the source cell by activating two protocol stacks, one for the source cell and the other for the target cell. The UE releases the connection with the source cell after a successful handover to the target cell.

3.2.2 Specific aspects of LTM handover

In all the handover types until 3GPP Release 17, a serving cell change is triggered by layer 3 (L3) measurements and is done by RRC signalling for change of primary cell (PCell) and a primary secondary cell (PSCell). All cases require reconfiguration of upper layers (e.g., RRC or packet data convergence protocol (PDCP)) and/or resetting of lower layers (e.g., MAC and/or PHY) which leads to longer latency, larger overhead, and longer interruption time than beam level mobility [5]. 3GPP Release 18 has introduced layer 1 (L1)/L2 based mobility also known as lower layer triggered mobility (LTM) [6], to enable a serving cell to change via L1/L2 signalling while keeping configuration of the upper layers and/or minimizing changes of configuration of the lower layers. This helps to reduce the latency, overhead, and interruption time during handover. During the LTM, the user plane is continued whenever possible (e.g. intra-DU), without a reset, with the target cell to avoid data loss and the additional delay of data recovery.

The overall procedure for LTM is shown in Figure 3-5.

Figure 3-5: High-level signalling of LTM handover procedure (from [Nokia 2022]) (Nokia, 2022).

The overall procedure is described as follows:

1. The UE sends a MeasurementReport message, including L3 quality measurements of the serving and neighboring cells, to the gNB, which controls the PHY, MAC, and RLC layer.
 2. Based on the L3 measurement report, the CU decides to use LTM
 - 3-4. The CU initiates LTM candidate preparation and requests to prepare the configuration of potential candidate cells for the UE.
 5. The gNB transmits an RRCReconfiguration message to the UE, including the configuration of one or multiple LTM candidate target cells. The UE stores the configuration of LTM candidate target cell(s) and transmits an RRCReconfigurationComplete message to the gNB.
- The UE may perform downlink (DL) synchronization and timing advance (TA) acquisition with the candidate target cell(s) before receiving the LTM cell switch command.
6. The UE performs L1 measurements on the configured LTM candidate target cell(s) and transmits lower-layer measurement reports to the gNB.

8-9. The gNB decides to execute the LTM cell switch to a target cell and transmits a MAC control element (MAC-CE), triggering the LTM cell switch. The UE switches to the configuration of the LTM candidate target cell.

10. The UE detaches from the source cell and performs the random-access procedure towards the target cell if TA is not available.

11. Upon successful random access to the target cell, the UE context is released from the former cell, and a path switch towards the target cell is performed. In LTM, the UE may perform partial or full MAC reset, may re-establish radio link control (RLC), and may perform data recovery with packet data convergence protocol (PDCP) during the cell switch.

3.2.3 Key performance indicators and HO decisions

The following mobility performance indicators are considered as key to affect deterministic communication:

- **Radio link problems (RLP):** Occur when N310 consecutive out-of-sync indications are received from lower layers signalling that the channel quality between the serving cell and the UE is deteriorating.
- **Handover failures (HOF):** Declared when random access to the target cell is not successful. This can indicate that the target cell signal at the time of HO execution is not stable enough for the UE to connect to the target cell.
- **Ping-pong (PP) events:** Occur when a UE successfully hands over to a target cell but returns to the previous serving cell within 1000 ms, indicating unnecessary handovers that cause service interruption, signalling overhead, and outages.
- **Reliability:** Measured as the ratio of total outage time to total service time, as outages can result from both failed and successful handovers.
- **Cell preparation events:** Its number is analysed to evaluate the signalling overhead on the radio interface between UE and the serving cell, as well as the overall network signalling overhead.
- **Resource reservation:** During handover preparation, the target cell reserves resources for the UE including random access preambles, radio resources, buffers, UE identifiers, etc. Resource reservation is quantified by calculating the duration between cell preparation and release for a UE, normalized by the number of drops, UEs, and simulation time to determine the network-wide resource reservation percentage per UE.

In LTM-based handover, a critical factor influencing latency and service interruption is the selection of the target gNB. While this decision is vendor-specific, it is commonly based on a

hysteresis-like approach. In this method, the handover is triggered only when the target gNB's RSRP surpasses the serving gNB's RSRP by a predefined threshold for a sustained period. Additionally, to prevent excessive handovers, a new handover procedure is restricted within a set time window following the last successful handover.

To improve RLP, PP effects, and HOF, an adaptive handover decision technique is proposed for step 8 of Figure 3-5, that takes into consideration RSRP's previous values and system state. It is outlined below.

3.2.4 HO decision based on LMMSE prediction of RSRP values

Unacceptable delay or even call dropping events may happen when a user leaves a coverage area but cannot connect reliably to new cell smoothly, which needs proper handover management. The basic assumption adopted is that an accurate prediction of channel state between a UE and the neighbouring gNB may provide efficient resource and handover management and avoid unacceptable degradation of the service quality. Additionally, the only way to guarantee continuous services, without any need to reserve the huge number of resources across the whole network, is the implementation of passive resource reservation policy. This kind of approach can pre-reserve a certain amount of bandwidth in the coverage areas that will probably be visited by users, which avoids reserving bandwidth over the whole system and therefore a lot of unnecessary resources can be saved.

The basic assumption adopted is that an accurate prediction of channel state between a UE and the neighbouring gNB may provide efficient resource and handover management and avoid unacceptable degradation of the service quality. Rather than relying on a traditional hysteresis-based handover decision, an adaptive approach is proposed to simultaneously predict PL3 (the RSRP measurements filtered at L3) measurements from both the serving and neighbouring gNBs. The assumption is that users are configured to continuously perform RSRP measurements of the synchronization signal block (SSB) at intervals ranging from 20 to 160 ms. As described in the LTM-HO proposal, to mitigate signal fluctuations caused by fast fading and measurement inaccuracies, the raw measurements undergo initial filtering at the UE using a moving average filter, forming the L1 measurements. Subsequently, an L3 filtering process is applied using a one-pole infinite impulse response (IIR) filter to further smooth out residual variations in PL1 (the RSRP measurements at L1) and enhance measurement accuracy. Over these measurements, the application of an adaptive linear minimum mean square error (LMMSE) prediction Δ samples ahead of time [7] is proposed, to include in the reserved set of target gNBs those whose channel state is more promising in the future. Capturing the PL3 values of the serving and neighbour gNB at time t in vector $x(t)$ Capturing the PL3 values of the serving and neighbour gNB at time t in vector $x(t + \Delta) = b(t) + H(t)x(t)$

where $b(t)$ and $H(t)$ are computed using the MMSE criterion from past observed samples of $x(t)$. The target gNB is then selected as the one with the highest L1 RSRP value if it is 3dB above the value of the serving gNB. This method ensures that the handover decision is based on a more informed trend, leading to a more stable signal level post-handover and reduced PP effects.

The LMMSE predictor intends to capture the correlation in PL3 due to the pathloss and the shadowing to predict future values of PL3 and at the same time remove the residual multipath fading components. To that end, the values of Δ samples have to lie between the decorrelation time of fast fading and the decorrelation time of shadowing. The Table 3-1 describes the approximate values of lags for decorrelation of PL3 depending on the vehicle speed. According to these speeds, the optimum Δ must lie between 21 and 699 samples for the speeds in the simulated scenario. A precise value must be validated in each scenario.

UE speed (Km/h)	Shadowing in PL3 decorrelation time (s)/ samples	Multipath fading in PL3 decorrelation time (s)/ samples
25	28 s / 1400 samples	0.0489 s / 20 samples
50	14 s / 700 samples	0.0246 s / 10 samples

Table 3-1: Decorrelation times for shadowing and multipath fading depending on the UE speed. Sampling time of RSRP is assumed 20 ms.

3.2.5 Results

For the generation of RSRP and Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) traces of a UE moving through an environment, pathloss, shadowing, and multipath fading channel models were adopted as described in [8]. Furthermore, the conventional lognormal shadowing model has been enhanced with spatial correlation and correlation among gNB sites, according to the models in [9]. Seven base stations sites, each serving 3 gNB sectorized at 120 degrees cells have been deployed with a frequency reuse of 1/6. Other settings are described in Table 3-2 assuming maximum traffic load in the computation of the interference.

Parameters	Values
Environment	3GPP compliant 7 gNB, 3 sector urban macro scenario with 250 m inter-site distance, UMa channel model, spatial and inter-site correlation of shadowing
Antenna setting	10 m height at gNB, sectored 120 degrees, max gain 8 dB, azimuth and elevation patterns, 1.5 m at UE, omni, gain 0 dB.

PHY settings	3.5 GHz carrier frequency, 20 MHz bandwidth, reuse 1/6, SSB transmission periodicity 40 ms, receiver sensitivity -95 dBm
Configuration	simulation time 200 s, 50 users, speed of UE 25-50 km/h, per route simulation time 200 s, time resolution 10 ms, sampling time of RSRP signal 20 ms

Table 3-2: Simulation values used in the evaluation of predictive HO for a 3GPP setup.

Parameters	Values
Environment	3GPP compliant 7 gNB, each featuring 3 sector urban macro scenario at 200 m inter-site distance, UMa channel model, spatial and inter-site correlation of shadowing
Antenna setting	10 m height at gNB, sectored 120 degrees, max gain 8 dB, azimuth and elevation patterns, 1.5 m at UE, omni, gain 0 dB.
PHY settings	3.5 GHz carrier frequency, 20 MHz bandwidth, frequency reuse $\frac{1}{3}$, SSB transmission periodicity 40 ms, receiver sensitivity -95 dBm
Configuration	50 users, speed of UE 25-50 km/h, simulation time 200 s, time resolution 10 ms, sampling time of RSRP 20 ms

Table 3-3 Simulating values used in the evaluation of predictive HO for a 3GPP setup.

Figure 3-6 shows the CDF of the number of HO per minute, the number of PP, the number of HOF and the number of RLF, for the HO decisions based on the LMMSE predicted RSRP level. While a full validation of the time lags for the ahead prediction is ongoing, a two-tap predictor with lags $\Delta = [24 \ 28]$ samples exhibit improved performance as compared to conventional LTM handover in terms of number of PP and HOF. Those values are intrinsically tied to the delays of each step in the HO procedure in Figure 3-5(whose values are described in [10]).

Figure 3-6: Performance of the LMMSE prediction-based HO decision on RSRP values as compared to the conventional LLM HO. The CDF of the RLP, the number of HO, the number PP, the link reliability, the number of cell preparations and the number of resource reservations are shown.

Figure shows that the HO decisions based on the prediction of the RSRP values using LLMSE filtering, results in a significant reduction in the number of RLP (-62% in median), the number of HO (-62% in median) and the number of PP (-27%), at the expenses of some mild increase in the number of cell preparations (+2.8%) and resource reservations (+1.7%). In terms of quality of service, the link reliability is improved from 98.78% to 99.1%, which entails a lower number of service interruptions. No HOF were observed in the scenario described. The Matlab code including the generation of the scenario, the simulation of HO procedures and evaluation are uploaded in the project GitLab. Extensive results and comparison with non-linear AI-based approaches ([11]) are to be reported in an upcoming publication.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/predictive-llm-ho-upc>

3.3 Data Unit Groups

Applications often send data which does not fit as payload into a single IP packet. As a result, a single Application Data Unit (ADU) is fragmented into smaller chunks with a maximum length of each chunk determined by the underlying computer network and its Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU). The set of packets that carry the entirety of a single ADU are hereby defined as a Data Unit Group (DUG). For high-throughput, low-latency applications such as Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR) media applications, collectively called eXtended Reality (XR) applications, this can lead to situations where a single packet loss can lead to the loss of the whole ADU for the application. The same applies for closed-loop automation digital twinning applications that require a wide range of monitoring data of the real world to create the digital twin for on-demand decision making; Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) scenarios have similar KPIs when exchanging sensing measurements from hundreds of (mobile) devices with the cellular network for further processing.

Since some ADUs are more important than others for the Quality of Experience (QoE) for the application user or the accurate performance of a digital twin, it can be useful for the network to be aware of the difference of importance between the ADUs, to be able to down-prioritise (or even drop) the least important packets in case of congestion.

Techniques have been developed in 5G as per [12] to convey "XR metadata", including importance within the flow, associated with a "PDU Set" (i.e., set of packets transporting an ADU) to the network. The sending application determines the metadata and associates it with ADUs (e.g., within individual packets). The network uses the importance of packets to determine which packets to drop in case of congestion.

Within this document, the group of packets that transport a single ADU is designated as a "Data Unit Group" (DUG). The purpose is to define a mechanism for conveying importance

(within the DetNet service flow) and related metadata of DUGs to DetNet routers, to make it available for enhanced queuing, shaping, scheduling, and pre-emption decisions.

This document aims primarily at extending the DetNet IP Data Plane [13] in an initial revision of this draft, and may be extended to Multi-Protocol Label Switching (MPLS) [14] and MPLS over User Datagram Protocol (UDP)/IP data plane options [15] in future revisions.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/dug-enabled-detnet-router-and-controller>

3.4 Seamless roaming through Wi-Fi 7 MLO

A comprehensive study on achieving deterministic communication within a dynamic hybrid network by leveraging Wi-Fi 7's Multi-Link Operation (MLO) and Ethernet is presented. The research focuses on enhancing seamless mobility and deterministic communication using an AI model trained to predict Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and classify the connection between a station (STA) and Access Points (APs).

The primary aim is to efficiently manage network flows using real-time mobility data and machine learning predictions, enabling adaptive network management that optimizes performance under changing conditions. The entire project is implemented and tested within the ns-3 simulation environment, featuring a hybrid network setup as illustrated in Figure 3-7.

This setup includes a mobile station, two fixed APs, a server, and an offboard controller, all operating in an obstacle-free environment. The station, acting as the source node, communicates with the server, the destination, over Wi-Fi 7 with MLO across three frequency bands: 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz, and 6 GHz. The station connects to one AP at a time, while both APs communicate with the server via Ethernet.

The decision-making process for STA-AP connectivity is based on evaluating KPIs such as latency, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). The controller is responsible for handover evaluation, determining the optimal AP for the STA.

Figure 3-7: Network Configuration Implemented in the ns-3 Simulator.

The controller receives data from the STA and trains a Neural Network (NN) to make these decisions. Data collection occurs at regular intervals, capturing features like the STA's (x, y) coordinates, speed, direction, and distance from each AP. The KPIs, including latency, RSSI, and SNR, serve as targets acquired during simulations. Various trajectories, both linear and curvilinear, are tested to create the dataset.

The employed NN architecture combines a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network with a Binary Classification NN, as shown in Figure 3-8. This combination leverages the LSTM's ability to predict KPIs, allowing the Binary Classification to determine in advance if a handover is necessary and the precise timing for its execution. This approach promises to enhance network performance by ensuring timely and efficient handovers.

Figure 3-8: Employed AI Model Combining LSTM and Binary Classification Neural Network.

Data acquisition was conducted at regular interval of 10 ms, capturing information across various linear and curvilinear trajectories to build a diverse dataset and to develop a robust neural network model capable of accurately predicting the most suitable Access Point (AP) for different movement patterns. The collected data includes the station's position (x, y), speed, direction, and the distance to each of the two APs, along with latency, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) for each frequency band and AP. This results in a comprehensive dataset comprising 18 features structured as follows: $(x_{STA}, y_{STA}, \text{speed, direction, } d_{STA,AP1}, d_{STA,AP2}, \text{lat}_{B0,AP1}, \text{SNR}_{B0,AP1}, \text{RSSI}_{B0,AP1}, \text{lat}_{B1,AP1}, \text{SNR}_{B1,AP1}, \text{RSSI}_{B1,AP1}, \text{lat}_{B2,AP1}, \text{SNR}_{B2,AP1}, \text{RSSI}_{B2,AP1}, \text{lat}_{B0,AP2}, \text{SNR}_{B0,AP2}, \text{RSSI}_{B0,AP2}, \text{lat}_{B1,AP2}, \text{SNR}_{B1,AP2}, \text{RSSI}_{B1,AP2}, \text{lat}_{B2,AP2}, \text{SNR}_{B2,AP2}, \text{RSSI}_{B2,AP2})$, where B0, B1, and B2 correspond to the 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz, and 6 GHz channels, respectively.

The input features for the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model include $x_{STA}, y_{STA}, \text{speed, direction, } d_{STA,AP1}$ and $d_{STA,AP2}$. These were selected based on a correlation analysis, which showed that using velocity components (v_x, v_y) and fixed AP coordinates instead of speed, direction, and distance did not enhance data correlation, as the AP positions remain constant being the APs fixed in the environment and v_x, v_y are stable in linear trajectories.

The LSTM model was trained on this dataset, applying a mask to disregard any unused frequency bands of an AP, with the goal of predicting KPIs (latency, SNR, and RSSI) for each

band and AP. The training and validation losses achieved during this process are illustrated in Figure 3-9.

Figure 3-9: Train and Validation Losses of the LSTM.

The predicted KPIs from the LSTM model, derived from the training process, are illustrated in Figure 3-10 and Figure 3-11, highlighting the model's performance for both linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Figure 3-10: Predicted KPIs for a linear trajectory. The acquired values are represented in blue, while the predicted values are shown in orange. Missing values are excluded based on the applied mask. The first row displays the KPIs, i.e. latency, SNR, and RSSI (from top to bottom), for AP1 across Band0 (2.4 GHz), Band1 (5 GHz), and Band2 (6 GHz) (from left to right). The second row presents the KPIs for AP2 in the same order.

Figure 3-11: Predicted KPIs for a curvilinear trajectory. The acquired values are shown in blue and predicted values in orange, excluding any masked values. The first row shows the KPIs, i.e. latency, SNR, and RSSI (from top to bottom), for AP1 across Band0, Band1, and Band2 (from left to right), while the second row displays the corresponding KPIs for AP2.

The predicted KPIs are fed into the Classification Neural Network (NN) as inputs. This network outputs one of six possible classes, each corresponding to a specific frequency band and AP combination:

- Class 0: 2.4 GHz band for AP1
- Class 1: 5 GHz band for AP1
- Class 2: 6 GHz band for AP1
- Class 3: 2.4 GHz band for AP2
- Class 4: 5 GHz band for AP2
- Class 5: 6 GHz band for AP2

During training, labels are assigned according to the following rule to reflect the channel of the AP with better performance in latency, SNR and RSSI:

$$label_i = \arg \min_{j \in \{0, \dots, G-1\}} W_{ij}$$

$$\text{where } W_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0.33 \cdot lat_{i,3j} + 0.33 \cdot X_{i,3j+1} + 0.33 \cdot X_{i,3j+2}, & \text{if all } X_{i,3j}, X_{i,3j+1}, X_{i,3j+2} \neq -1 \\ \infty, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where:

- X represents the entire dataset matrix,
- i identifies a specific data sample (a row corresponding to a particular time instant),
- j identifies a specific group (latency, SNR and RSSI related to the same bandwidth and AP),
- G is the total number of groups in the dataset matrix

The training loss for the Classification NN is shown in Figure 3-12.

Figure 3-12: Training Loss of the Classification NN.

To evaluate the model's performance, a confusion matrix is used, as depicted in Figure 3-13. This matrix highlights the discrepancies between the actual labels and those predicted by the Classification NN, demonstrating that the model has an accuracy of 99,1%.

Figure 3-13: Confusion Matrix Showing Discrepancies Between Actual and Predicted Labels.

The integration of neural network (NN) models into the ns-3 simulator has been implemented to optimize the network handover process. This integration leverages multithreading, data processing, and network flow management to ensure efficient task handling and responsive operation under dynamic network conditions.

Continuously collecting position and velocity data from the STA allows for the computation of speed, direction, and distances to access points (AP1 and AP2). These calculations consider the most recent five data points, which are normalized and processed using the LSTM model previously described. This model predicts future network states over a short horizon, corresponding to the next ten-time instants.

The predictions generated by the LSTM model are refined through a masking and denormalization process. Subsequently, these refined predictions undergo a new normalization and are fed into a Classification NN. This classification model determines the optimal AP for the STA to connect to, thereby managing network flows effectively.

This adaptive system responds to changes in network conditions, ensuring that network flows are adjusted in real-time to maintain optimal performance.

From an implementation point of view, to improve efficiency, such a procedure has been reorganized so that a task queue system is designed to handle concurrent task execution

efficiently. This system is built using a thread-safe queue, allowing for the orderly processing of tasks in a multithreaded environment. The task queue handles multiple types of tasks, including data processing tasks that involve normalizing mobility data and processing it through the LSTM model to predict future network states. Once predictions are made, network flow management tasks refine the data and use a Classification NN to determine the optimal AP for the STA, thereby managing network flows. Flow adjustment tasks dynamically adjust network flows based on the Classification NN's output to adapt to changing conditions, ensuring optimal performance. Additionally, monitoring and logging tasks track system performance and log relevant data for analysis, helping to maintain the system's efficiency and responsiveness.

Task management is facilitated by a dedicated thread that continuously monitors the task queue, waiting for tasks to be enqueued and processing them to manage network flow accordingly. This ensures tasks are executed in a controlled manner, preventing race conditions and ensuring thread safety. The task enqueueing mechanism facilitates the addition of tasks to the queue by locking the queue, adding the task, and notifying the processing thread, ensuring tasks are promptly processed as they are added, maintaining the system's responsiveness.

A schematic representation of this procedure is shown in Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14: Diagram Illustrating the Handover procedure based on NN models. The black arrows represent the sequential flow of data through the processing pipeline. The yellow arrows represent the coordination and distribution of tasks from the task queue to the relevant components, while the red ones represent the execution and management of tasks by the task management system.

Instead, as a baseline, the handover process is managed based on the distance between the STA and each AP. Hence, assessing periodically the position of the STA, its distance to each AP is calculated. If the STA needs to connect to the first AP (AP1) and is already connected, data transmission between the STA and AP1 continues until the next position assessment. Conversely, if the STA is connected to the second AP (AP2), the data transmission between the STA and AP2 is halted at both the application and MAC levels, and UDP frames are generated from the STA to AP1 at the application level. Similarly, if the STA needs to connect to AP2 and is already connected, UDP frames continue to be sent until the next position check. If the STA was previously connected to AP1, the running application is stopped, and a traffic flow between STA and AP2 is restarted. This process repeats at each position check.

A schematic representation of this procedure is shown in Figure 3-15.

Figure 3-15: Diagram Illustrating the Handover procedure based on distance STA-AP.

To assess the performance of the proposed optimized approach based on NN models, a comparative analysis focusing on the average latency throughout the simulation was conducted. This optimized approach was compared against the baseline method just described, where handover decisions are based only on distance.

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation, 120 different simulations were conducted. In these simulations, the STA starts moving from different initial positions within the environment and moves with various velocities generating both linear and curvilinear trajectories.

Therefore, Table 3-4 presents the average performance metrics for both methods, including average latency, standard deviation, packets sent and received, and packet delivery ratio.

Table 3-4: Comparison of Average Performance Metrics for Both Methods, Including Average Latency, Standard Deviation, Packets Sent and Received, and Packet Delivery Ratio.

Method	Average latency [ns]	Average standard deviation latency [ns]	Average Number of packets sent	Average Number of packets received	Average Packet delivery ratio [%]
Optimized Handover NN approach	171594138	105648694	119501.65	115702.23	94.77
Handover based on distance STA-AP	174201458	83269943	138861.63	134933.92	95.23

Based on these metrics, the proposed optimized approach using neural networks outperforms the distance-based method in 63.33% of the simulations. Additionally, when considering the average latency across all 120 simulations, the proposed method demonstrates a lower mean latency compared to the distance method, with a difference of 2607320 ns.

The data generated and used in the scientific publication is available at this repository:” <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/wi-fi-mlo-roaming>”. However, the source code for this item cannot be shared due to confidentiality.

4 Standalone Demos

4.1 Localisation and Sensing

This section describes the domain-specific system architecture of the localisation and sensing demo which presents the solution for a deterministic data plane introduces a Packet Data Unit (PDU)-like concept for all IP traffic. The overarching system architecture for multi-domains and technologies is provided in Figure 4-1 which illustrates the two domains, 3GPP and DetNet, as a representation of multiple domains (and technologies). Note that the 3GPP domain is considered to be DetNet-enabled, following the considerations in 3GPP’s TS 23.501 ([12]). In case of a 3GPP domain, the 5G System (5GS) is exposed as a logical DetNet transit router where each User Equipment (UE) and User Plane Function (UPF) (N6 interface) represents a port of the DetNet router. The 5G control plane sees the newly added Time Sensitive Communication and Time Synchronisation Function (TSCTSf) allowing external (DetNet) control plane applications to interact with the 3GPP system (that acts as a DetNet router) for the purposes of time synchronisation-related service requests, reporting time synchronisation service statuses, and exposing topology-related 3GPP domain-specific information to external applications.

The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is also shown in Figure 4-1 to indicate the necessity to expose link and port monitoring information about the DetNet-Enabled 3GPP user plane (Uu, N3 and N9 interfaces) to the external system.

Figure 4-1: System Architecture for DetNet-Enabled 3GPP and DetNet Domains.

The following two sub-sections focus on the data plane and as well as the domain-internal control plane design and implementation.

All rights are reserved for the implementation of DetNet Router and Controller and the repository is available here [PREDICT 6G / DUG-Enabled DetNet Router and Controller · GitLab](#).

4.1.1 Data Plane

Implementations of DetNet data plane solutions show that it is possible to achieve deterministic networking across multi-domain and multi-technology networks, with the goal of fully integrating deterministic networking into cellular networks. The objective is to provide deterministic networking capabilities for all IP traffic without the need for dedicated tunnels, and to allow deterministic packet treatment for packets carrying a single ADU. The PDU set concept for all IP traffic (referred to as DUG) is incorporated into a DetNet-enabled data plane for Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functionality (PREOF) packet treatment across an entire DUG. To enable routers to identify packets as DUG, DUG is introduced as an extension to the IPv6 header, as motivated in Section 3.3.

To support DUG over DetNet routers, an extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) program is implemented. This implementation uses eBPF to communicate the significance and associated metadata of DUGs to DetNet routers, enabling PREOF behaviour across DUG-aware DetNet routers. The DUG-enabled router uses eXpress Data Path (XDP) hooks to parse the DUG header and perform additional logging. The XDP hook also sets a cycle time for simple queuing, against which all incoming packets are evaluated. Frames are rerouted to a user-space memory buffer by the AF_XDP socket (XSK) through eBPF maps. DUG packets are stored in the maps and redirected to AF_XDP for access via actions in the XDP hook. XDP actions determine the fate of a network packet after processing by an eBPF program, including XDP_PASS (allowing the packet to continue through the normal network stack) and XDP_REDIRECT (redirecting the packet to user space or another network interface).

As Figure 4-2 suggest, in the XDP hook, the eBPF map BPF_MAP_TYPE_XSKMAP is used to redirect packets to user space using the `bpf_redirect_map` function, where they are processed by the AF_XDP component. This is primarily done to enable DetNet routing using the PREOF of DUG.

Figure 4-2: eBPF for DetNet Router.

For monitoring as provided in Table 4-1, the eBPF implementation has been extended to provide live DUG-related networking characteristics from each DetNet router, supplying data points to an NWDAF or DNC.

Table 4-1: Monitoring Data Points of DUG enabled DetNet Router.

Data Point	Description
dugs	Total number of DUG packets per second
ipv6 flows	The total number of IPv6 flows per second handled in active cycles
ipv6 pktcnt	The total number of IPv6 packets per second handled by DetNet router
late packets	The ratio of packets outside a cycle over active cycles per second
link latency	The communication latency between two DetNet routers
round trip	The average Round Trip Time (RTT) per second between two DetNet routers

The monitoring logic involves both the XDP and AF_XDP hooks. Initially, packets are captured by the XDP hook. XDP redirect is enabled using the BPF redirect map, redirecting packets along with their arrival time to AF_XDP. Once AF_XDP opens the socket using the xsk_socket function and starts receiving packets, it compares the packet arrival time with the current time to check if they fall within the 1 millisecond cycle time duration. Packets within this cycle time are further verified for being DUG by checking their optional type. Additionally, the flow ID of each packet is verified, if different, the count is added within the cycle time duration. Packets that did not arrive within the cycle time are also counted as late packets as Figure 4-3 suggest.

Figure 4-3: Monitoring and PREOF by AF_XDP.

As suggested by Figure 4-4 each DUG packet has a unique sequence number for identification. After monitoring, the next step is enabling the PREOF condition. Identified DUG packets are replicated and sent to the receiver. At the receiver end, the XDP hook verifies the arrival of DUG packets using their unique sequence numbers. Duplicated packets are removed using XDP_DROP, while all other packets are allowed to pass to the kernel using XDP_PASS.

Figure 4-4: PREOF by XDP.

4.1.2 Control Plane

This section provides the details on the implementation of a DUG-enabled DetNet router and its domain-internal control functions, i.e., TSCTSFS and NWDAF for a 3GPP domain and a DetNet Controller (DNC) for a DetNet domain, respectively. The overarching drawing is provided Figure 4-5 and forms the structure of this section, which focuses on three functional interfaces between a domain and the network digital twin (NDT), as illustrated and described in Figure 4-1 (Ntmf, Ndmf, Npce) and denoted as API (short for Application Programming Interface) in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-5: Conceptual Implementation of a Data Unit Group-Enabled DetNet Router and DetNet Controller.

The focus point for this section is to provide insights to the APIs from the DNC to the NDT (aka AICP), categorised into topology exposure, data monitoring and network (service flow) management.

The component blocks are illustrated in Figure 4-6 depicting the functional software blocks and interfaces among them. The NDT block represents the entire end-to-end AICP which obtains domain-specific topology and capability information via the Ntmf interface. This Service-Based Interface (SBI) offered by the NDT allows the TSCTSFS and DNC to report topology and capability information in a unified fashion; the IETF drafts [16] and [17] form the basis for this interface. For simplification purposes, the TSCTSFS and DNC are implemented as a single python3-based web-server with its own SBI, allowing the NDT to administer, revise and delete service flows via the Ndnrc interface.

Figure 4-6: Exposure and Service Flow Management Implementation.

The actual compute hosts on the data plane (i.e., UE, UPF and DetNet Router (DNR)) operates a dedicated DNRapi software component which comes with its own SBI towards the TSCTSF/DNC, i.e. Ndnr. The DNRapi, implemented in Python as a web-server, allows the TSCTSF (in a 3GPP domain) or DNC (in a DetNet domain) to request the compute host to handle a new service flow utilising the DUG concept. The DNRapi interfaces with the compute host using python-based system i/o libraries. To load the XDP hook that implements monitoring, xdp-loader¹ (part of the xdp-tools implementation) is being used. As described in the previous section, the data plane implementation comes as an AF XDP-based object that can be directly started with a set of arguments describing the service flow, e.g. receive/send interface, service flow identifier, PREOF settings. These settings are handed down via the Control Plane APIs from the NDT to the DetNet Router.

4.2 TSN on Wi-Fi

To validate the effectiveness of the TSN on Wi-Fi the proposed approach under real-world operational conditions, demonstrating its benefits in delivering time-sensitive traffic and optimizing energy efficiency was tested. This evaluation is conducted using our Wi-Fi IIoT testbed, which is built with commercially available TWT-capable STAs and APs.

The TWT testbed consists of 10 STAs, one AP, and a PC host, as shown in Figure 4-7. To showcase the advantages of utilizing TWT for traffic transmission scheduling, an application that enables boards to transmit a single TX of 4,800 bytes (divided into 8 frames with 600-byte payloads) to an Ubuntu host every 10 beacon intervals was developed. To minimize potential transmission delays caused by AP beacon overlaps, all boards initiate data generation precisely 8.192 ms after the Target Beacon Transmission Time (TBTT). This timing accounts for the AP's behaviour, where each beacon interval includes two consecutive beacons (the second with a hidden SSID), each requiring up to 3.5 ms of airtime. Synchronization is achieved by aligning the boards' clocks with the AP using the Wi-Fi Timing Synchronization Function (TSF), which the Wi-Fi driver exposes to the traffic-generating application through ESP-IDF. Additionally, to prevent Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) traffic, the Ubuntu host's MAC and IP addresses are pre-stored in the boards' firmware.

Two configurations were evaluated:

1. **NoTWT:** Each board immediately attempts to access the channel and transmit data as soon as it is generated, simulating a standard Wi-Fi network without TWT.

¹ <https://github.com/xdp-project/xdp-tools/tree/main/xdp-loader>

- 2. **TWT:** Each STA establishes a TWT agreement with the AP, ensuring non-overlapping TWT Service Periods (SPs). Specifically, in ascending ID order, each STA's SP begins 9.42 ms after the previous one, preventing overlap between subsequent TXs.

Each configuration was tested for over 12 hours, during which more than 35 million frames were captured, corresponding to over 48,000 transmissions per STA.

Figure 4-7: Testbed components: 10 TWT-compatible stations (left side), Wi - Fi AP (right side), and Wireshark live.

The results obtained are shown in Figure 4-8 and Figure 4-9, which show the latency measured for each STA in the two different scenarios, TWT and NoTWT.

Figure 4-8: NoTWT scenario. The measured latency is reported for each STA. Since STAs coordinate access using the Distributed Coordination Function (DCF), this results in increased latency due to unpredictable access delays and potential collisions.

Figure 4-9: TWT scenario. The measured latency is reported for each STA. Each STA is assigned a dedicated TWT Service Period (SP), ensuring exclusive access to the wireless medium during its scheduled transmission window.

When TWT is not utilized, the latency fluctuates significantly due to the random backoff mechanism. On average, the median latency is 58.2 ms, with a standard deviation of 12.6 ms.

More critically, no STA is able to transmit its traffic within 65.3 ms of its generation time more than 95% of the time (as indicated by the vertical dashed line in Figure 4-8).

A full transmission consists of 8 frames, which are not sent sequentially. Instead, other STAs gain access to the channel between frame transmissions, further delaying the completion of transmissions for all STAs. These findings clearly demonstrate that the NoTWT configuration is inadequate for time-sensitive networking, as it introduces unpredictable delays.

In contrast in Figure 4-9, the TWT mechanism ensures consistent latency performance by scheduling STAs according to predefined time slots, with TXs allocated by the AP. Under TWT, the median latency is 49.1 ms, with a standard deviation of 2.5 ms, representing 16% and 80% reductions, respectively, compared to the NoTWT scenario. Here, STAs complete all frame transmissions before another STA begins, allowing those with stricter latency requirements to be prioritized.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/polito-tsn-on-wi-fi>

5 Integrated Demos

5.1 Non-deterministic devices and networks

This section provides an overview of the implementation on the solution that can provide deterministic operation over technology domains lacking in-built deterministic capabilities, thus providing only non-deterministic services out of the box.

PREDICT-6G system provides E2E deterministic services spanning over multiple heterogeneous network domains and technologies. Most of the domains implement deterministic networking capabilities, though there can be cases where PREDICT-6G's E2E deterministic service needs to incorporate domains and/or devices which lack in-built deterministic capabilities. The handling of such scenarios was first discussed in Section 4.7 of ([18]) where device- and network-side requirements and considerations were introduced. Then Section 5.3.5 of ([19]) elaborated the options for extending user-plane of non-deterministic networking domains with capabilities to make them capable to participate in a E2E deterministic service. In the next step, Section 5.1 of ([2]) reported on the implementation of flow monitoring for non-deterministic networks which consisted of Measurement Agents (MAs) implemented as a packet processing software module using Intel's Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK). The MAs were able to measure throughput, jitter and depending on the deployment scenario (i.e. single or multiple MAs deployed) they could perform downlink and uplink delay and loss measurements. Section 5.5 of ([1]) provided a detailed methodology and apparatus to realize the required user-plane extensions discussed in Section 5.3.5 of ([19]) for incorporating non-deterministic network segments into E2E deterministic services of the PREDICT-6G system.

The method and apparatus presented in Section 5.5 of ([1]) extensively extended the MAs introduced in Section 5.1 of ([2]) with capabilities to emulate deterministic capabilities over non-deterministic network segments and created a unified but configurable and adaptive entity referred to as the MDP Agent. Section 5.5 of ([1]) gives a detailed description of the concept and operation of the MDP Agent, here is only a brief overview is provided for the sake of convenience (for further details the reader is encouraged to check Section 5.5 of ([1]).

MDP Agent improves the determinism in existing non-deterministic networks in three areas:

- provides real-time flow level insight to the service level and performance of packet delivery
- obtains the demand of each flow in terms or resources, time sensitivity and resiliency

- implement adaptive self-calibrating mechanisms that are capable of dynamically enforcing the separation of flows and allocation of resources per each flow according to their demand

To achieve this, MDP Agent is implemented as a software module that can be inserted into the data-plane at multiple locations and supports a set of functionalities that is selectively activated depending on the deployment/location of the specific MDP Agent in the E2E path. The architecture of the implemented MDP Agent is shown in Figure 5-1.

* Based on own measurements, configuration, flow and service QoS requirement awareness

Figure 5-1: Architecture of the MDP Agent.

The time sync (F1) functionality is a compulsory part of the MDP Agent, but the measurement actions, scheduling and traffic shaping, de-jittering and packet replication and elimination functionalities (F2-F5) are pluggable one and they can be added or removed from the MDP Agent based on the actual deployment scenario.

The MDP Agent is implemented in the Nokia Open Lab providing a real test network including two technology domains, (1) a non-deterministic 5G network and (2) an IP transport network. The MDP Agent implements MDP OpenAPIs to provide the PREDICT-6G MDP capabilities and for

integration with the AICP components to enable automated deterministic service provisioning. The MDP Agent based solution is part of the deterministic services for critical communication use case demonstration and corresponding detailed results will be reported in D4.3 due in June 2025.

Figure 5-2 shows a scenario in which two robotic arms are connected via a non-deterministic 5G network and IP network. The robotic arms perform a collaborative task in which one of the robotic arms acts as leader and the other robotic arm is following the movement of the first one. The robotic arms have to perform their movement in synchronization what requires a deterministic service with QoS targets of maximum 50ms end-to-end latency and maximum 5ms end-to-end jitter. The 5G and IP networks transfer not only the traffic of the robotic arms but also traffic from other users which is considered as background traffic with no required QoS targets in the validation. In the initial state of the test (denoted as Period 1 in Figure 5-2), only the “F2: Measurement actions capability” of the MDP Agent is enabled, the determinism ensuring capabilities (F2-F5) are deactivated. The bottom half of Figure 5-2 shows the per network segment measurements for the robotic arm traffic whereas the upper part shows the end-to-end measurements for both for the robotic arm traffic and the background traffic provided by the MDP Agent. The measurements show that the background traffic overloads the radio network segment serving the Follower robotic arm and due to this the latency and jitter deterministic QoS targets of the robotic arm traffic are not met.

Figure 5-2: Validation of MDP Agent operation

After activating the “F3: Scheduling and traffic shaping” and “F4: De-jittering” capabilities of the MDP Agent (denoted as Period 2 in Figure 5-2), the PREDICT-6G system with the MDP Agent is able to guarantee the deterministic QoS targets over the 5G and IP networks even though they lack in-built deterministic capabilities. The amount of the background traffic is the same in Period 2 as in Period 1, still the latency and jitter of the robotic arm traffic is significantly reduced on the radio network segment connecting the Follower robotic arm and thus the end-to-end latency and end-to-end jitter falls below the deterministic QoS targets. As the top right corner in Figure 5-2 shows, the QoS target success rates are 100% for Period 2. The presented validation results shows that MDP Agent can provide improved determinism in networks without inherent deterministic capabilities.

The code of the implementation is not public but available to reviewers on request (NOK contact: Péter Szilágyi, peter.1.szilagyi@nokia-bell-labs.com).

5.2 Industrial cross-domain TSN

5.2.1 Development of extensions for operation of 5GS as TSN bridge. Time-based schedulers on 3GPP

As staged in 3GPP TS 23.501 ([12]), 5G System can be integrated as a TSN bridge by using TSN-Translators at Device and Network sides (DS-TT and NW-TT respectively).

In Deliverable 2.2 ([2]), it was introduced a software switch with TSN capabilities that can behave as TSN translator, providing TSN ports at TSN Translators points, support of 802.1Qbv ([20]) time-based scheduling with time slices and guard period, as well as support of Frame replication 802.1CB [21], and it is compatible with 802.1Qcp ([22]) YANG model. Since then, the TSN translator has evolved as detailed below.

The time-based scheduling, based on 802.1Qbv, is enhanced in several ways. On one hand, the standard traffic classification is extended including classification based on packet information (layers 2,3 and 4 and/or ingress port) and S-Label from DetNet (by coding the S-Label into the DSCP field of the IP header). On the other hand, the synchronous scheduler includes an adaptative scheduler where a reinforcement learning agent optimize the scheduler configuration to synchronize the external traffic with the time window.

Standard de-jittering implementation is improved with two additional methods. One is an Adaptative de-jittering using a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) Agent to stabilize the jitter. The other is a Smart de-jittering which takes advantage of a developed 3GPP network digital twin to train a DRL agent that perform de-jittering of packets not including the ingress timestamp.

For Frame replication and elimination for reliability (FRER), the R-TAG (redundancy tag) is extended in order to add a timestamp of the packet with the purpose of calculate the one-way delay across the 5G network.

In addition, VxLAN tunneling is supported to extend L2 networks across 5G networks as PDU sessions of type Ethernet are not fully supported at 5GS.

Regarding performance, the TSN translator has been characterized concluding that the software switch reaches up to 2.50 Gbps, which is high enough to cope with the deterministic use cases, adding a latency of $50\mu s$, which is acceptable in environments with latencies in the order of milliseconds.

About KPI framework, the TSN translator generates metrics such as number of packets/octets sent/received, replicated/drop/disordered packets or one way delay.

Additionally, the Smart Factory use case, which is included in the *Industrial Cross-Domain TSN* activity, has been demonstrated, including the TSN Translators at device and network sides.

The corresponding detailed results will be reported in D4.3 due in June 2025. A brief summary of latency results is shown in Table 5-1.

KPI	Objective (ms)	Measured (ms)
Max. Expected Latency UL (no de-jittering)	20	9.09
Max. Expected Latency DL (no de-jittering)	20	6.99
Max. Network Jitter UL	5	3
Max. Network Jitter DL	5	6

Table 5-1: Latency measurements.

Repository available here: <https://github.com/5Tonic/gopsav2>

5.2.2 Introduction of TSN capabilities in the 3GPP network backhaul

To ensure deterministic communication within the core-to-gNB link, a TSN domain with FRER has been incorporated. This mechanism enhances network reliability through frame replication and elimination between the UPF and gNB. A Centralized User Configuration (CUC) has been designed to enable the configuration of the three switches.

Figure 5-3: TSN enhanced 3GPP 5G NR.

The CUC receives information regarding VLAN headers and MAC addresses to which FRER-TSN should be applied, as well as the direction (UPF→gNB or gNB→UPF). This latter parameter is crucial since the ingress switch is always responsible for replicating the information and distributing it through different paths toward the destination. In contrast, the egress node is responsible for eliminating duplicate frames to prevent redundant information from being sent out.

Based on the provided information, the CUC will send the appropriate configuration to each switch. Once the rules are activated, when traffic reaches the ingress node, it will inspect the VLAN header and MAC addresses to determine whether FRER-TSN should be applied. If so, the ingress node translates the MAC addresses from the non-TSN domain into MAC addresses of the TSN domain. This node also replicates the frames and forwards them through different paths. These frames are identified using the 802.1CB R-TAG, a header that reserves 2 bytes to store the frame's sequence number.

As shown in Figure 5-3, the intermediate node filters the traffic and forwards it to the destination. Finally, the egress node is responsible for discarding duplicate frames and translating the MAC addresses used in the TSN domain back into their original MAC addresses.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/tid-tsn-domain>

5.2.3 Updated Deterministic End-to-End Multi-Domain Use Case

Building on the previous work presented in [1] –where the evolution of the multi-domain use case (featuring a remotely controlled robot dog enhanced with gesture-based control and a Digital Twin for industrial scenarios) was introduced—the final validation of the architecture is reported now.

Experimental Setup and Key Findings

The final experiments were conducted in the 5TONIC laboratory, where the MDP was integrated with the AICP to create a fully deterministic end-to-end network. Detailed measurements were taken under realistic operational conditions, yielding the following key results:

- **End-to-End Latency:** The system consistently achieved a round-trip time (RTT) of 14–15 ms, corresponding to a one-way latency of approximately 7.5 ms in 99% of the measurements.
- **Packet Loss:** No packet losses were observed for the deterministic flows, even under high levels of background traffic injected at various ingress points.

These results validate that the enhanced architecture—featuring seamless TSN support across Wi-Fi, Ethernet, and a more stable Ericsson-provided 3GPP TSN domain, along with integrated DetNet routers using XDP and eBPF—can meet the stringent requirements of industrial automation and other latency-critical applications. To isolate the contributions of each network domain, background traffic was introduced at multiple ingress points. Despite the additional load, the time-sensitive traffic maintained its deterministic guarantees. The Table 5-2: Measured latency contributions. summarizes the measured latency contributions.

Component/Domain	Latency (ms)
Wi-Fi TSN Domain	2.0-2.5
5G TSN Domain	4.0-4.5
Ethernet TSN Domain	<1

DetNet Data Plane Overhead	<1
Overall E2E (One-Way)	≈7.5
Overall E2E (RTT)	14-15

Table 5-2: Measured latency contributions.

The experimental outcomes confirm that the upgraded multi-domain deterministic networking framework achieves robust end-to-end performance. The seamless integration of TSN capabilities across heterogeneous domains and the reliable operation of the DetNet-based data plane collectively ensure low-latency, packet-loss-free communication.

Repository available here: <https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/p6-tsn-xdp-switch>

6 Open APIs

The OpenAPIs are an important part of the service-based architecture of the PREDICT-6G system, allowing for flexible MS implementation options and the adoption of new technology domains with reduced effort.

The OpenAPI design was first introduced in Section 6 of ([18]). In the next phase those domain level AICP Management Services which require interaction with the MDP were analysed in Section 11 of ([19]). In the last step of the OpenAPI related work, Section 6 of ([19]) reported the human readable summary for each API or set of APIs, where it was foreseen that interaction should happen between the MDP and a corresponding domain level AICP Management Service.

This subsection briefly summarizes the specified PREDICT-6G OpenAPIs and provides a pointer to the YAML definition of the respective OpenAPIs.

6.1 Times sync

The Time Sync API follows the operation described in Section 8.2, 9.4, 11.3.1 of ([19]) with regards to 3GPP MDP-AICP integration.

The YAML definition of the Time Sync API is available at:

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/Predict-6G-TimeSynch.yaml>

6.2 Deterministic service provisioning, decommissioning, updates

This set of APIs are responsible for the provisioning, decommissioning and update of deterministic services. The detailed description of the service provisioning API is provided in ([1])

The YAML definition of the service API is available at (for multiple MDP technologies):

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/3gpp-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/detnet-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/tsn-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/wifi-configuration.yaml>

6.3 Exposure of services: topology, capabilities, resources

This set of APIs are responsible for exposure of topology, capabilities and resources. The detailed description of the Exposure API is provided in [1].

The YAML definition of the Exposure API is available at:

https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/topology_exposure_v2.0.yaml

6.4 Measurements and data collection

This set of APIs are responsible for measurement and data collection. The detailed description of the Measurement Collection API is provided in [1].

The YAML definition of the Measurement Collection API is available at:

https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/data_collection/PREDICT-6G_Data_Collection.yaml

7 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the implementations of PREDICT-6G innovations for enhancing the determinism in the multi-domain and multi-technology Data Plane. The document includes the final results of the implementation of these enhancements, which demonstrate how these innovations improve determinism.

In addition, the deliverable reports the reference links to the repositories where the implementation code is stored.

Some of the implemented innovations have been integrated into successful PREDICT-6G demos, such a 3GPP 5G mobile network enhanced with user plane improvements that provide deterministic capabilities, and a cross-domain integration of TSN, Wi-Fi and 3GPP using DetNet in a real testbed using commercial equipment

The document's appendix also includes references to the Open APIs developed for the MDP capability to expose the determinism towards the control plane.

8 References

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9 Appendixes

9.1 Appendix A

The implementations provided in this document can be found in the GIT repositories listed in the following table.

Repository name	GIT URL
Dynamic Scheduling	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/dynamic-scheduling-upc
Predictive LLM Handover for 5G	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/predictive-llm-ho-upc
Data Unit Groups	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/dug-enabled-detnet-router-and-controller
P6 TSN XDP Switch	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/p6-tsn-xdp-switch
P6 DetNet	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/P6-DetNet
Sensing Framework	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/ide-sensing-framework
TSN redundancy to interference/attacks	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/intel-tsn-redundancy-to-interference-attacks
Time-based schedulers on 3GPP	https://github.com/5Tonic/gopsa
Aligning rTWT and IEEE 802.1Qbv	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/twtscheduler
POLITO TSN on Wi-Fi	https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/polito-tsn-on-wi-fi